

Citation

Jinadasa, L., & Wickramasinghe, V. (2005). IT industry labour turnover: The reality. In *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Sri Lanka Studies*, University of Kelaniya, Kelaniya, December 16-18. ISBN 955-9044-54-0.

IT industry labour turnover: The reality

Abstract

At the time of regaining independence, though the Sri Lankan economy was open to free trade, it was mainly dominated by agriculture. Since the adoption of liberal economic policies in 1977, new industries have been created, and the export structure has become diversified. One of such emerging industries is Information Technology (IT). After the mid-1990s, an expansion in the IT industry has been witnessed with many local and international companies setting up operations to cater to the international market. As IT companies build on knowledge workers, absorbing qualified employees is the focal point. In the competitive IT labour market, companies make substantial investments by adopting various strategies to recruit qualified knowledge workers, creating a high IT labour turnover rate in the industry. This not only influences the performance and stability of the IT industry but also increases the costs of recruitment and selection of knowledge workers. In this context, the arising IT labour turnover issues should be addressed. This paper investigates reasons for IT industry labour turnover and related retention issues. In the study, a survey questionnaire was used, and 158 randomly selected knowledge workers (all graduates) responded. Data was analyzed using SPSS software. The findings gave an insight into the knowledge worker turnover behaviour, in which only 6% satisfied with their current job with the current employer, while 24% intended to leave the current employer if they got a better job offer from another IT company, only in Sri Lanka. Being a lucrative global industry, another 24% intended to leave if they got a job offer or a permanent residency in a foreign country. A detailed analysis of IT industry labour turnover, individual expectations, management issues in the IT industry, and practical implications of the findings is discussed.

Keywords: Labour turnover, information technology industry, information technology professionals

1. Introduction

In Sri Lanka, the IT industry has developed rapidly over the past few decades. With globalization and economic liberalization, Software giants in the world started investing heavily in Sri Lanka. In addition, software development firms started operations with the expansion of IT knowledge in the country.

The software industry in Sri Lanka started in the early 1980's. Initially, almost all software companies were catering solely to the local market. With the increase in global demand, Sri Lanka experienced a boom in the software industry during 1997, with many local and international organizations setting up operations. Since then, over 80 software development companies are in operation in Sri Lanka, and many more are to commence commercial operations.

According to the Information & Communications Technology (ICT) Manpower survey (1999), 43.6% of ICT professionals are working in software development companies. Further, the study says that the annual growth rate of software development manpower is 14.7%. Due to the recent increase in demand for IT Knowledge workers, demand for qualified computer professionals, especially university graduates, is high, and retention is a problem. Leading companies in the field snap up fresh computer science graduates. This situation has led the IT industry to a competitive edge.

The IT industry thrives on knowledge workers. It is obvious that recruiting more and more qualified software engineers has been a focal point of this industry. This has created rivalry between competitors where each firm tries to steal the best people from other competitors, offering them better prospects in terms of salaries, experience, and working environment. Due to this fact, labour turnover is among the highest in the software industry when compared to other industries in which professionals are employed.

When turnover rate hits hard, a company's focus should turn to retaining the employees already on board. To reduce the turnover rate, organizations have to investigate staff turnover and retention issues. Although there are various studies conducted in the world in this field, no such study can be found in the Sri Lankan context in the IT industry. Therefore, to fill the gap in Sri Lankan literature, the study was conducted to address the arising IT labour turnover issues.

The specific objectives of the study were to 1) investigate IT professionals' perceptions regarding job-fit, 2) investigate labour turnover intention of IT professionals, and 3) analyze job-fit and labour turnover intention trends in terms of gender, age, and tenure. In the investigation, turnover is regarded as a voluntary job movement that creates a vacancy in an organization.

2. Literature Review

There are three key factors affecting labour turnover (Beames2001), i.e., organizational factors (e.g., culture, opportunities, job level and status, job security, and flexible work practices), individual factors (e.g., personality, career interests, health, and family support), and environmental or external factors (e.g. employment opportunities, economic conditions, and changing technology). Thus, labour turnover can be reduced by enhancing employees' job satisfaction and affective commitment.

Labour turnover trends were studied against Age, Work Experience, Tenure, Kinship Responsibilities, Education, Promotional Opportunity, Pay, Distributive Justice, Work Environment, Alternative Employment Opportunity/Job Market, Job Commitment, Job Satisfaction, and Behavioural Intention to stay or leave (McCarthy et al, 2002). However, the results of such studies are mixed. Josefek and Kauffman (2003) were unable to find any statistically significant correlation between labour turnover and any of the traditional predictors such as age, tenure, gender, wage, education, firm size, or performance.

It was found that a significant number of employees could be retained if retention strategies of promoting greater autonomy, professional development, managerial support, or improved professional practice environment had been introduced (McCarthy et al, 2002). "Intent to

stay” and “intent to leave” have been discussed as the single most reliable predictors of actual turnover behaviour.

In the specific IT industry context, Paré et al.(2001) have identified a multidimensional set of human resources (HR) practices that were likely to increase retention among IT employees. They revealed that IT specialists are particularly sensitive to four types of HR practices: distributive justice, competence development, empowerment, and recognition. On the other hand, Carayon et al (2003) revealed that gender plays a role in turnover in the IT industry.

A study on staff turnover in India software industry (Rathi, 2003) has identified 'retention and motivation of software professionals' as the top HR challenge faced by the industry. Managing the aspirations, career satisfaction, and met expectations are predictors of employee turnover (Rathi, 2003). Further, the results revealed that person-culture (P-C) fit, the fit between personal beliefs and values of an individual, and person-job (P-J), the fit between the job challenges and achievement orientation of a person, are the two important variables that are closely related to employee turnover.

A similar study was carried out to explore the determinants of turnover intention among technical staff in IT companies in China (Mian, 2003). The results revealed that job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and search behavior are the main three factors for turnover intention. Employees who are loyal to their companies and who are satisfied with their jobs intend to stay in their companies; employees who are not searching for other jobs intend to stay in their companies.

The impact of employee turnover in an organization is dramatic. According to Latimer (2002), staff turnover can be broken down into three phases: Separation (Disassociation of the employee from the position), replacement/acquisition, and knowledge transfer and training. Separation costs may include severance pay, costs associated with an exit interview, and outplacement fees. Replacement costs are the costs of a hire, HR processing costs for screening and assessing candidates, the time spent by hiring managers interviewing candidates, and travel and relocation expenses. Finally, orientation and training costs.

According to Hinchcliffe (2003), some turnover is, of course, unavoidable and even desirable, such as retirements, promotions, interdepartmental transfers, or layoffs. But one should be more concerned with the voluntary turnover of top performers. The review of IT industry literature in the USA suggests that the cost of turnover is generally about 1.5 times the salary of a departing employee, but this figure can vary widely based on the nature of the job and the organization, where turnover costs were found to be about 0.75 times annual salary for non-exempt employees and 2.0 times annual salary for professionals.

3. Research Methodology

The survey method was used in the investigation. The questionnaire was developed to collect information on job-fit and intention to leave/quit the job, and the reasons for such, together with demographic information of respondents. The list of companies that are registered in the Software Exporters Association (SEA) was used, as it gives a sound base for a homogeneous sample. 500 questionnaires were distributed among randomly selected IT knowledge workers who were working as either software developers/engineers, project managers, or consultants, of which 166 questionnaires were received back. Out of this 166,

8 were incomplete. Thus, the final sample consisted of 158 IT knowledge workers. Of the 158, 78 per cent of respondents were in the 26-35 age group. There were 72 per cent male respondents and 28 per cent female respondents. Nearly 50 per cent of the sample was married. All respondents were graduates. 9 per cent of them had postgraduate qualifications.

Most of the respondents were specialized in either IT or the Engineering field. 71 per cent of the sample were programmers. Further managerial and consulting positions were handled by another 10 per cent and 12 per cent, respectively. 40 per cent of the sample have less than 2 years of working experience in their current job, while 50 per cent have experience between 2 and 6 years. 71 per cent of the sample employees were doing their first job in the current organization, while 29 per cent had a work history. Several semi-structured interviews were conducted with randomly selected respondents to get in-depth views on the subject matter.

4. Findings and Discussion

4.1. IT knowledge workers' job-fit with respect to their current job

As shown in Figure 1, 23 per cent of the respondents do exactly the right job according to their level of expectations. 61 per cent of the respondents state that they were able to meet their job expectations only up to a certain extent. For 9 per cent of respondents' current job was not matched to the individual expectations completely. 7 per cent stated that they were not sure whether their job fit their level of expectations.

Figure 1. IT staff member's job-fit

5.2. IT knowledge workers' turnover intention

As stated in the literature, turnover has a strong relationship with the Intention to leave. Therefore 2 questions were used to find out the data on IT staff intention. Question 'What would you be doing in 5 years in terms of your career' was used to measure their intention directly, while question 'If you leave your current job, what would be the most applicable reason' was used to cross-check their intention in a different manner. Data were illustrated using Figures 2 and 3 as follows.

Figure 2. Career intention in 5 years

Figure 2 shows the career intentions of the respondents in 5 years. It indicates that 42 per cent were expecting to have a change in their current role within the company. For example, 15 per cent of respondents wanted to leave the company to change their field of work. Another 15 per cent wanted to leave the country. Another 14 per cent was in the other category (None of the above), in which most stated that they would leave due to personal commitments and/or further studies. Figure 3 shows the results for the most applicable reason if the respondents decide to leave the company within the next five years. The findings, as illustrated in Figure 3, indicate that only 6 per cent of the respondents want to really stay in their current job. 40 per cent of respondents stated that they would leave due to personal commitments or due to higher studies. 24 per cent stated that they would leave if they got a foreign job offer or a permanent residency in a foreign country. Another 24 per cent were leaving only if they were offered a better job. The findings shown in Figure 3 confirm their certain intention indicated in Figure 2.

Figure 3. Career intention to leave the job

5.3. Job fit and turnover intention trends

Responses for job-fit and turnover intention were analyzed in terms of personal demographic variables of gender, age, and tenure. Job-fit and turnover intention with respect to Gender are shown in Figures 4 and 5. The level of job-fit indicated as ‘Yes, exactly’ according to individual expectations on figure 4 shows a decrease on female than that of males. But expectations on job-fit indicated as ‘Up to a certain extent’ show higher responses for this category for female staff. Similarly, Figure 5 shows that female staff want to change the role of their job more than that of males.

Figure 4. Gender vs. job-fit

Figure 5. Gender vs. turnover intention

According to Figure 6, there are no remarkable differences in job-fit with respect to age.

Figure 6. Age vs. job-fit

According to Figure 7, most of the employees who are in the age group 20- 25 want to change the role of their job. They want to play a different role or work in a different area in the same organization. It is clear that respondents belonging to the age group of 31-35 would like to continue their current job.

Figure 7. Age vs. turnover intention

According to Figure 8, the 2nd category, ‘Up to a certain extent’ shows that there is an upward trend with respect to tenure.

Figure 8. Tenure vs. job-fit

According to Figure 9, the highest number of respondents who were in the 'Continue the job' category have 6-8 years of experience (Tenure) in the current organization. Similarly, the highest number of employees who want to leave the country were in the '6-8 yrs' group. Most of the employees with 2- 6 years of experience want to change their job roles.

Figure 9. Tenure vs. turnover intention

6. Conclusions

This research addressed the IT Staff turnover issues in software development companies in Sri Lanka. In the study, a survey questionnaire was used, and the findings were based on 158 responses received from randomly selected knowledge workers who were randomly selected from the registered companies that were registered in the Software Exporters Association (SEA).

When it comes to turnover intention, it was found that more than 50% of employees do not want to quit their current job within the next 5 years. But 80% out of this category expect a change in their role, basically career advancement, within the organization. So, this poses a huge challenge for an organization to retain IT knowledge workers unless they have a proper career development/promotion plan in place. 15% of employees have already decided to quit their jobs due to various reasons such as better job, personal commitments, and higher studies. It was also observed that another 15% of IT professionals were about to leave the country. It was interesting to note that the majority of IT knowledge workers were satisfied with their current jobs, even though they had decided to leave the country.

When analysing the job-fit, it was found that only 23% of employees indicated that their job fits well with their level of expectations. More than 60% stated that it was only up to a certain extent. It implies that, even though employees are satisfied with their current job, it does not fit well with their level of expectations. It will lead to quitting the current job whenever they get an opportunity to find a well-fitted job. There are no remarkable differences in responses on gender with either turnover intention or job-fit. However, there are slight differences in responses in terms of age and tenure with either turnover intention or job fit.

Overall, this research study addressed the turnover behaviour of IT professionals in large-scale software development companies. Its findings gave an insight into the current organizational and industrial situation in the software industry. So this knowledge would be helpful to any similar organization. Even though the research is based on the IT industry in Sri Lanka, the problem domain is more common to IT sectors, irrespective of the country of study.

In order to reduce the turnover rate, any company has to focus on its organizational factors. As turnover has a direct association with job satisfaction, a company should evaluate its organizational factors to improve the level of satisfaction of its staff. The recommended areas can be listed as follows.

- The senior management should be more supportive and friendly towards its staff.
- Frequent staff rotation is needed in order to provide new exposure and interest in the work.
- A proper career advancement plan should be implemented in each organization.
- Regular assessment of the salary and other company benefits compared to prevailing market conditions.
- Accept the challenge of turnover by doing knowledge sharing and training for the remaining staff to reduce the gap arise due to staff turnover.

The following are some possible areas of further work that may improve the relevance and importance of the study.

- Increase the size of the sample and population to go for a generalized solution for the IT industry.
- Expand the conceptual model by finding other related variables to turnover.
- More specific and advanced research to find out the associated cost of turnover.

References

Beames, C. (2001). *About turnover and retention* (White paper). WRDI Institute Pty Ltd.

Carayon, P., Hoonakker, P., Marchand, S., & Schwarz, J. (2003). *Job characteristics and quality of working life in the IT workforce: The role of gender*.

Hinchcliffe, R. (2003). *The cost of turnover*. LIMRA International.

Josefek, R., & Kauffman, R. (2003). *IT human capital and the information systems professional's decision to leave the company*.

Latimer, D. (2002). *The cost of IT staff turnover: A quantitative approach*. University of Tennessee.

McCarthy, G., Tyrrell, M., & Cronin, C. (2002). *National study of turnover in nursing and midwifery*.

Mian, Z. (2003). *An empirical study on the causal model of turnover intention in Chinese IT companies*. Retrieved June 9, 2004, from <http://www.mercerhr.com/>

Rathi, N. (2003). *Human resource challenges in the Indian software industry: An empirical study of employee turnover*. Retrieved July 24, 2004, from <http://www.mercerhr.com/>